

POZAPROGRAMOWA PRACA MŁODZIEŻY STUDENCKIEJ NADDNIPRIANSKICH UNIWERSYTETÓW XIX WIEKU

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Streszczenie. Temat artykułu ujawnia osobliwości rozwoju szkolnictwa wyższego Naddnipsrianschyną, które były uwarunkowane wydarzeniem historycznym XIX wieku. i wpłynął na stopniowy rozwój edukacji. Szczegółowy jest wpływ wewnętrznych i zewnętrznych uwarunkowań społeczno-kulturowych, co znalazło odzwierciedlenie w obiektywnym zróżnicowaniu procesu edukacyjnego przyszłych specjalistów w dziedzinie specjalizacji przyrodniczych i humanitarnych.

Przedmiotem badania była merytoryczna treść pracy, niezwiązanej z audytem w kontekście najlepszych światowych tradycji edukacyjnych wyznaczonego okresu historycznego. Celem artykułu jest analiza treści wariacyjnej nie audiologicznej formy pracy przez pryzmat światowych tradycji edukacyjnych XIX wieku. Metodologiczny zestaw badań został opracowany metodami biograficznymi, chronologicznymi, etapowymi, historyczno-genetycznymi, historyczno-pedagogicznymi i porównawczymi.

Opracowanie bazy źródłowo-studyjnej umożliwiło ustalenie, że w badanym okresie nie było jasnych formalnych regulacji dotyczących tego, jaki powinien być system dydaktyczny nowo odkrytych uniwersytetów na Dnieprze na Ukrainie. Postępowe postacie, pedagodzy aktywnie pracują nad rozwojem etnograficznej treści edukacji i edukacji.

Analiza problemu tytułowego opierała się na przemyśleniu najlepszych teoretycznych osiągnięć badanej epoki, które problematyzowały wysoce ideologiczne poglądy pedagogiczne i przekonania ówczesnych członków wydziału. Refleksja nad określonym tematem opierała się na holistycznej aksjologicznej, humanistycznej i osobiście zorientowanej konstrukcji badawczej.

Potwierdzono, że działalność edukacyjna nauczycieli badanych uniwersytetów miała na celu dywersyfikację dyscyplin i form zgłaszania studentów, organizację działań estetycznych i środowiskowych (wycieczki po terytorium, zakładanie towarzystw ochrony środowiska itp.).

Przeprowadzona analiza historyczna i pedagogiczna pokazuje, że dla wszystkich dyscyplin akademickich nauczanych na uniwersytetach w Dnieprze na Ukrainie w XIX wieku. system zajęć klasowych charakteryzował się względnym zjednoczeniem. Nie towarzyszące zajęcia i formy zgłaszania studentów dla każdego przedmiotu były indywidualne, ponieważ odzwierciedlały specyfikę każdej dyscypliny naukowej.

Należy zauważyć, że potrzeba utworzenia lokalnej specjalności określonego systemu społecznego wymagała od przedstawicieli uniwersytetów skorelowania elementów procesu studiów regionalnych i szkolenia zawodowego z zadaniami nauczania i edukacji. Udowodniono, że działalność nauczycieli opierała się na idei indywidualnego rozwoju świadomości i odpowiedzialności indywidualnej, obywatelskiej i narodowej. Należy zauważyć, że taka progresywność poglądów często nękała znaczące prześladowanie ze strony obecnych przywódców politycznych, ale nie dewaluowała pod wpływem destrukcyjnych procesów tamtych czasów.

Materiały drukowane przekonują, że działalność nauczycieli uniwersytetów w Dnieprze w badanym okresie nie tylko ukierunkowała studia nad lokalnymi studiami i edukacją młodzieży studenckiej, ale również stała się jednym z czynników rozwoju pedagogiki narodowej. Lokalna

wiedza o działalności pedagogicznej przedstawiciele badanych instytucji edukacyjnych opierała się na szkoleniu wysoko wykwalifikowanych specjalistów i edukacji prawdziwych patriotów. Podkreślono praktyczną orientację i znaczenie nauk przyrodniczych dla coraz głębszego przemyslenia fizycznych i geograficznych cech ich ojczystej ziemi, które korelowały z edukacją patriotyczną i estetyczną w badanym okresie.

Słowa kluczowe: praca pozalekcyjna, młodzież studencka, Naddniprianszczyna, proces społeczno-kulturowy.

EXTRACURRICULAR WORK OF THE STUDENT YOUTH OF NADDNIPRYANSHCHYNA UNIVERSITIES OF THE XIX CENTURY

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Abstract. The subject of the article reveals the peculiarities of the development of the natural science field of higher education of the Naddnipryanshchyna, which were conditioned by the historical events of the XIX century and affected the gradual development of education. The influence of internal and external socio-cultural determinants, which were reflected in the subjects' differentiation of the future specialists' educational process in natural and humanitarian specialties, is detailed.

The subject of the study was the substantive content of extracurricular work in the context of the best world educational traditions of the defined historical period.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the differentiated content of extracurricular form of work through the prism of world educational traditions of the XIX century.

The research tools for the study were biographical, chronological and content, incremental, historical, pedagogical and comparative methods.

The study of existing sources and database made it possible to establish that in the period under the study there was no clear formal regulation as to what should be the didactic system of the newly discovered universities of Naddnipryanshchyna. Progressive figures and teachers actively worked on the development of ethnography-oriented content, forms, principles, methods and means of education.

The analysis of the titled problem was based on the analysis of the best theoretical developments of the studied epoch, which challenged the highly ideological pedagogical views and beliefs of the professorial teaching staff. A rethinking of the subject was based on a holistic axiological, humanistic, and personally-oriented study construct.

It was confirmed that the educational activity of the universities teachers under the study was aimed at the diversification of the disciplines and forms of students' reporting, as well as at the organization of aesthetic and environmental measures (excursions around the territory, establishment of environment protection societies, etc.).

The conducted historical and pedagogical analysis shows, that for all the academic disciplines that were taught at the universities of the Naddnipryanshchyna during the XIX century, the system of face-to-face classes was characterized by relative unification. Extracurricular activities and forms of student reporting for each subject were individual because they reflected the specific character of each scientific discipline.

It is noted that the need for the formation of a local lore specialist of a specific social system required from the representatives of universities to correlate the components of the process of regional studies and professional training with the tasks of teaching and education. It was proved that the activity of teachers was based on the idea of individual development, civil and national consciousness and responsibility. It is highlighted that such progressiveness of

views often suffered considerable harassment on the part of the current political leaders of the day, but did not devalue under the influence of destructive processes of that time.

Printed material confirm that teachers activities of Naddniprolyanshchyna universities during the studied period not only directed the study of local studies and education of student youth, but also became one of the factors of national pedagogy development. Local lore content of pedagogical activity of the studied educational institutions representatives was based on the training of highly skilled specialists and the education of true patriots. The importance of natural sciences for a more profound rethinking of the physical and geographical features of their native land, which was correlated with patriotic and aesthetic education in the period under study, was emphasized.

Subsequently, the content of the scientific and pedagogical searches of graduates proved the importance and fundamental meaning of the theoretical and practical directions of local lore and pedagogical activity, which was carried out by their scientific mentors - teachers.

Keywords: extra-curriculum work, student youth, Naddniprolyanshchyna, socio-cultural process.

ПОЗААУДИТОРНА РОБОТА СТУДЕНТСЬКОЇ МОЛОДІ НАДДНІПРЯНСЬКИХ УНІВЕРСИТЕТІВ ХІХ СТОЛІТТЯ

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Анотація. Тема статті розкриває особливості розвитку природничого напрямку вищої освіти Наддніпрянщини, які обумовлювалися історичною подією XIX ст. та позначилися на поступальному розвитку освіти. Деталізовано вплив внутрішніх та зовнішніх соціокультурних детермінант, які віддзеркалювалися у предметній диференціації навчально-виховного процесу майбутніх фахівців природничих та гуманітарних спеціальностей.

Предметом дослідження виступила змістова наповненість позааудиторної роботи у розрізі кращих світових освітніх традицій означеного історичного періоду.

Метою статті є аналіз варіативного змісту позааудиторної форми роботи крізь призму світових освітніх традицій XIX ст.

Методологічним інструментарієм дослідження послуговувалися біографічний, хронологічно-змістовний, поетапно-проблемний, історико-генетичний, історико-педагогічний та порівняльний методи.

Опрацювання джерелознавчої бази дало змогу встановити, що в період, який досліджується не було чіткої офіційної регламентації стосовно того, якою має бути дидактична система нововідкритих університетів Наддніпрянської України. Прогресивні діячі, педагоги активно працювали над розробкою краєзнавчо-орієнтованого змісту навчання та виховання.

Аналіз титульної проблематики засновувався на переосмисленні кращих теоретичних напрацювань досліджуваної епохи, які проблематизували високоідейність педагогічних поглядів та переконань тогочасного професорсько-викладацького складу. Відрефлексування визначеного предмету будувалося на врахуванні цілісного аксіологічного, гуманістичного та особистісно зорієнтованого конструкту дослідження.

Підтверджено, що освітньо-краєзнавча діяльність викладачів досліджуваних університетів була спрямована на урізноманітнення дисциплін і форм звітності студентів, організацію естетично-екологічних заходів (екскурсії по території краю, створення природоохоронних товариств тощо).

Проведений історико-педагогічний аналіз свідчить, що для усіх навчальних дисциплін, які викладалися в університетах Наддніпрянської України упродовж XIX ст. система аудиторних занять характеризувалася відносною уніфікацією. Позааудиторні заняття та форми звітності студентів для кожного предмета були індивідуальні, оскільки відображали специфіку кожного наукового напрямку.

Зазначається, що потреба у формуванні краєзнавчо обізнаного спеціаліста конкретної соціальної системи потребувала від представників університетів співвідносити складові процесу краєзнавчо-професійної підготовки із завданнями вчити та виховувати. Доведено, що діяльність викладачів будувалася на ідеї індивідуального розвитку особистості, громадянської і національної свідомості та відповідальності. Зауважено, що така прогресивність поглядів нерідко зазнавала значних утисків зі сторони діючого політичного керівництва, проте не девальвовувалася під впливом руйнівних процесів того часу.

Друковані матеріали переконують, що діяльність викладачів університетів Наддніпрянщини досліджуваного періоду не лише спрямовувала краєзнавчо-освітню підготовку студентської молоді, але й стала одним із факторів розвитку національної педагогіки. Краєзнавчий зміст педагогічної діяльності представників досліджуваних закладів освіти базувався на підготовці висококваліфікованих фахівців і вихованні справжніх патріотів. Підкреслено практичну зорієнтованість та значущість природничих знань для все більш глибокого переосмислення фізико-географічних особливостей рідної місцевості, що співвідносилося у досліджуваній період із патріотичним та естетичним вихованням.

Ключові слова: позааудиторна робота, студентська молодь, Наддніпрянщина, соціокультурний процес.

Introduction. The orientation of the educational paradigm to the formation of the individual, as well as preparation for life involves deepening knowledge about the environment, the history of the native land and regional identity. At all stages of the history of Ukraine, the spread of regional education contributed to the social, economic, cultural and national development of the state. The introduction of progressive ethnographic, historical and pedagogical traditions is based on axiological, acmeological, human-centered indicators and meets the requirements of the National Doctrine of Education Development in Ukraine, the State National Program "Education" (Ukraine XXI Century).

Some aspects of the problem under study are found in the works of V. Andrushchenko, T. Zavgorodnaya, V. Syrotyuk, N. Demyanenko, A. Sukhomlinskaya, M. Sheremet and others. However, the issue of the extra-curricular work content of Naddnipryanshchyna in the context of the best educational traditions of the given century remains to be studied.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the differentiated content of extracurricular form of work through the prism of world educational traditions of the XIX century.

In accordance with the purpose, *the tasks* of the study are the following:

- to analyze the state of the investigated problem;
- to follow the peculiarities of pedagogical theory and practice development during the investigated historical epoch;
- to popularize national historical and pedagogical experience.

The methodological research tools for the study were biographical, chronological and content, incremental, historical, pedagogical and comparative methods.

The Kharkiv University. The teachers of the Kharkiv University provided numerous theoretical and practical recommendations to representatives of general educational institutions regarding how to correctly study and compile a description of the territory of the region. The Dean of the History and Philology Faculty G. Uspensky independently prepared an instruction for collecting statistical, topographical and historical data for secondary schools. His colleague, Professor I. Gut, developed a special project for conducting geodetic, meteorological and astronomical observations for gymnasiums. Similar methodological instructions were also compiled for the purpose of geographic data recording [2, p. 74].

In 1814, speaking at a regular meeting of teachers, Uspensky said: "... it is important for every nation to know the ancient and present condition of its land ..." [2, p. 74]. In order to direct the local lore work of teachers in the right direction, he developed a special program in 1815. For the purpose of its content filling the representatives of the university had to visit all the schools that were in the district. Structurally, the program contained two parts - general and special ones. The first part reflected the level of the educational process at schools, and the second – provided for the collection of local lore information by teachers and their pupils according to the plan.

In accordance with Uspensky's assumption, the collected materials, after being elaborated by experienced teachers, should have entered the circulation not only at secondary schools, but also universities. The scientist believed that only in this way it will be possible "to collect the necessary historical, topographical and statistical data, which the university still does not possess" [2, p. 74]. So, the high school teacher Zozulin collected nine notebooks of the topographical descriptions of the Poltava province.

Analyzing the local history and pedagogical plan of the professor, it becomes clear that it was based on the didactic principle of continuity in learning. In accordance with which, part of local lore knowledge was acquired by pupils at school, and deepened - in university conditions.

However, G. Uspensky's ambitious plan for the collection of local lore materials could not be fully realized in practice because of technical reasons. Although, the pedagogical content of the educational - linguistic project in the scientific regard was perfect. The compilation of newsletters proceeded rather slowly due to the fact that the materials sent to the Main College Committee of the Ministry of National Education contained a number of errors and a significant amount of unnecessary information. Technical gaps were caused by the directives of the Ministerial Committee, which sought to turn valuable materials into chaotic management statistics.

Professors of the Naddniprovyanshchyna universities, which were members of the regional lore scientific communities, had close cooperation with high schools, lyceums and schools. M. Sumtsov expressed his own pedagogical vision of what should be local lore excursions for students. At the regular meeting of the Pedagogical Department of the Kharkiv Historical and Philological Society (October 3, 1897), the scientist made a presentation: "On the issue of organizing local educational student excursions." In the introduction, the educator emphasized that recently in the pedagogical press, many wishes have been highlighted on how to properly organize and conduct a regional study tour for pupils. As a result, Sumtsov noted, teachers from Kharkiv University received a variety of questions from different regions from pedagogues-organizers of excursions, among them were the following:

- 1) "... what is interesting from the educational point of view in Kharkiv and the Kharkiv province?
- 2) What educational establishments and scientific societies are present in the region?
- 3) How are student excursions organized within the boundaries of the region? " [9, p. 2].

Professor Sumtsov wrote that when considering student excursions, "... I mean exclusively male secondary schools" [9, p. 4]. Although it is possible, the teacher argued, that all instructions could be used to conduct such activities at higher and lower secondary schools. The scientist was convinced that the smaller the age and the class of the pupils - the more difficult it is to organize them for this or that local lore event. The true teacher is the one who is able to organize walks so that his students will always be occupied with inspecting the area. However, according to the teacher, the walks should not be identified with educational excursions. It is best to organize excursions on the territory of the region with a group of students of 5-8 grades.

From a methodological point of view, the teacher recommended those educators who are preparing for the tour, "... to determine what you will show and how you will show it in advance, and how the shown things should enter into a complex system of meaningful comments" [9, p. 6].

Looking at the territory of his own region, Sumtsov proposed, first of all, to pay attention to the temples and monasteries, as well as to get acquainted with "church archeology and ancient books ..." [9, p. 7]. After that, you should visit museums "... not only urban, and especially university ones" [9, p. 7]. When listing numerous exhibits of the university exposition, he suggested that teachers should draw pupils' attention to the ethnographic, photographic and pottery materials. Professor of Kharkiv University noted that "university museums ... contain a mass of the highly valuable educational material that needs to be further studied in detail. Among them, there were the zoological, mineralogical and little-known numismatic rooms" [9, p. 8]. Sumtsov recommended visiting local factories and plants, which are a kind of driving force of industrial development of the region.

Concluding his report, Sumtsov emphasized that it was necessary to propose to the pedagogical department to elect a special Commission at the university, which would accumulate local lore material collected by regional professional educational institutions. According to the scientist, the data would be processed by university representatives and subsequently represented in the publications of the Historical and Philological Society. Representatives of the Naddnipyrianshchyna universities, which were members of scientific societies, developed ethnographically oriented visual materials that were actively implemented in the educational process of the above-mentioned institutions. In 1820 a member of the Kharkiv Naturalists' Association, Professor V. Chernyayev, conducted the first botanical expedition, which covered the territory of Poltava, Dnipropetrovsk, Bessarabia, Odessa and the southern coast of the Crimea. During the trip, the scientist collected valuable samples of the representatives of the flora of different regions of Ukraine. Reporting to the Academic Council of the Kharkiv University about the results of the expedition, the professor in one of his letters said: "... the plants collected for the past two years I passed on to the Kharkov gymnasium ..." [7, p. 163]. It was not the only collection that the teacher presented to the mentioned above institution. During his trip to European countries, Chernyayev collected

a new collection, which he wrote: "... I have the opportunity not only to transfer a more or less complete herbarist (Herbarium) to the university, as the correct guide for anyone who is studying botany, but also to pass on one herbarist to all the gymnasia that belong to the educational district of the university, ..." [1, p. 526].

In the summer 1832 Chernyaev went to the Tavia province to analyze the educational process of gymnasia and other educational institutions. It should be noted that during the time off work, the scientist, together with his teachers and students, conducted a study of the typical flora of the territory of the southern coast of the Crimea. All samples collected by them entered the museum collections of gymnasia.

Professor O. Potebnya made a significant contribution to the development of educational regional studies. He repeatedly organized meetings with the youth of the "narrowly-formed" educational institution - the Kharkov collegium (later - the seminary), in which he spoke "... about the historical past of the region, about our songs, about our poetry, and called for research and love, and the students with pleasure listened to him for hours" [72, p. 38-39].

The Kiev University. In the 1860's the issue of the opening of Sunday schools for adults became of paramount importance, and Potebnya was actively involved in this activity. The teacher prepared a Ukrainian primer, which was built on "full-fledged words"; the content was saturated with local material and was "completely deprived" of religious motives.

A significant contribution to the development of pedagogical regional studies at the Kremenets Gymnasium was made by the Society of Naturalists and the first Professor of Botany at Kyiv University V. Besser. The scientist made every effort to bring a zoological collection to the gymnasium, which contained a lot of exhibits of local representatives. The above-mentioned collection was more numerous than in the Vilno Medical and Surgery Academy. It consisted of varieties of fish (119 units), insects (2585 units), birds (453 units), mammals (79 units), molluscs (2220 units), as well as a number of specimens of reptiles, bats and worms.

The educator entered the history of regional studies not only as a famous researcher, who managed to combine medical practice and research of representatives of local flora and fauna, but also as the founder of the Kremenets Botanical Garden. On the territory of the mentioned garden there were systematically numerous excursions not only for pupils of general and professional educational institutions, but also for all interested persons.

The head of the Zoology Department of the University of Vilno, and later Professor of Kyiv University E. Eichwald introduced the visual materials of local lore content at Kremenets Lyceum at the high methodological level. This is how the graduates of the Lyceum describe the teacher in which he worked from 1819 to 1821: "... considering himself a natural scientist, he was a specialist in the zoology of the local fauna and in paleontology ..." [6, p. 112]. In 1829, Eichwald visited the Kremenets Lyceum in the framework of an expedition on the territory of Volyn, where he had the opportunity to get acquainted with the natural-historical exposition. This is evidence of the fact that at that time the lyceum owned the regional collections. Analyzing the seen, the scientist noted that in the above-mentioned educational institution it was necessary to create a museum of local lore, in which there should be a geological exposition. During the 5-month trip, the professor collected many samples for the museum, and repeatedly organized a two-week tour of the local limestone and chalk mountains. It

should be noted that Eichwald, while outside Volyn, continued to collect geological, botanical, zoological and paleontological collections for the museum in the territory of Odessa, Kherson and other territories [10]. Z. Fedorovich, the researcher of the creative heritage of E. Eichwald, in his work "Zarys rozwoju fizjografii Polski ze szczegolnym uwzglednieniem faunistyki (od czasow najdawniejszych do roku 1918)" emphasized that the professor was concerned not only with the replenishment of the collections of the local lore, but also the liceum museum [11].

V. Antonovich (Kyiv University), on his own initiative, prepared an archaeological map of Volyn, which was used in the educational process of the lyceum and gymnasium. This work consisted of two parts - the explanatory text and the actual map, on which the archaeological monuments of various types were marked with colored symbols.

In addition, the representatives from the Naddnipyrianshchyna universities expressed a lot of comments as to what the educational process should be. Thus, Davien noted that chemistry was not included in the list of gymnasium disciplines, which was an important basis for understanding the course of chemical processes in the nature of the region. Another disadvantage, according to the professor, was that natural history (ethnography) was studied by pupils in separate parts. On the initiative of the representatives of the high school on June 17, 1861, the approval of such a procedure of natural sciences teaching in gymnasia was:

1st form - mathematical and physical geography of the region (2 lessons per week);

2nd form - physical and chemical phenomena occurring in nature (1 lesson per week);

3rd form - characteristic of external forms of animals and plants, characteristic of the area of the region (2 lessons per week);

4th form - chemistry, which included the topic of chemical processes characteristic of the region (1 lesson per week);

5th form – zoology, containing topics in the region's zoology (2 lessons a week);

6th form - botany, which includes topics from the regional botany (2 lessons a week);

7th form - geology and mineralogy, which focused on the consideration of geological and mineralogical characteristics of the territory of the region (2 lessons a week) [4, p. XXIV-XXB].

In addition, the meeting considered the level of educational institutions' provision with educational materials. Initially, the professors stopped at choosing the most appropriate microscopes for the educational process. Then, they turned to the consideration of an extremely serious issue - the provision of educational institutions of different levels with natural collections. Professor A. Rogovich drew the attention of all those present to the fact that these collections can be collected locally by the teachers of natural sciences. Professor Kessler volunteered to help and make for them a special catalog of items that should have been included in the collection. Davien emphasized that, taking into account the research and material level of the university, only he can act as a sponsor and at the same time a compiler of all natural collections collected in the territory.

The purpose of the second Kyiv congress of naturalists was outlined at the opening by its organizer prof. K. Kessler. The teacher expressed his thoughts about the

fact that the subject of pedagogical meetings should be the discussion of the natural sciences teaching in secondary schools, as well as "... a detailed consideration of issues related to the compilation of natural collections at gymnasia and the purchase of other teaching aids for teachers of the Natural Sciences "[4, p. 10].

Considering foreign lore and pedagogical experience, Professor D. Bagaliy noted that European educators were following the fact that the acquaintance of the students "... first of all, with what they see next to and around themselves ..." [3, p. 14] began from the elementary school. The teacher believed that only under such conditions the pupils "... will revere, appreciate and love the land" [3, p. 15]. Professor repeatedly emphasized that many European nations had a great commitment to their local history, archeology, "... we see there even local museums ..." [3, p. 14]. For this reason, Bagalyi emphasized that the content of programs of folk schools, schools for adults and for extracurricular education should have involved the local history that would familiarize students with the historical events that took place in Slobozhanshchyna.

As a conclusion. On the basis of the foregoing, we see that the multifaceted educational and linguistic activities of teachers, which they realized practically during the XIX – early XX centuries, were not limited to the boundaries of the Naddniproshchyna universities. Employees of higher educational institutions provided theoretical and practical recommendations for teachers of local schools, gymnasiums and colleges on how to organize and conduct properly a local lore event. Thus, professors who were members of university research societies developed a lot of visual materials that were used by students of general education institutions to familiarize themselves with the region. In our opinion, the most significant manifestation of the introduction of the results of local lore and pedagogical activity of university teachers in the practice of educational institutions can be considered the holding of the first two nature researchers' congresses. At the congresses mentioned above, the teachers held several pedagogical meetings, which provided a lot of methodological recommendations for teachers of educational institutions. The results of fruitfully held congresses of nature researchers can be followed also in conducting numerous local lore events for the students not only of domestic, but also foreign general educational institutions.

The prospects of further researches are seen in the study of the axiological content of the creative heritage of pedagogical staff, who have made a significant contribution to the development of higher education in various regions of the world.

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